

THE TECHNOLOGY OF CREATING VALUABLE ATTITUDES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: There is increasing recognition of the value of inclusive education and the role of universal design for learning in supporting it. However, moves towards inclusion are taking place at different rates in different countries. Technology has considerable, but largely unused potential to support inclusive education of disabled people and other minority groups. In particular it can provide multiple means of presenting, representing and expressing learning and through AT enable disabled learners to overcome barriers they would otherwise experience to participating in the curriculum. It also has the potential to increase enjoyment and motivation. There is increasing evidence of the value of ICT and AT in supporting and improving the education of disabled people. Distance education has potential to increase educational access, but should not be at the expense of making institutional education accessible. However, not all the initiatives consider the needs of disabled people. Differentiated learning supported by technology has considerable potential, but is rarely used, largely due to lack of appropriate teacher education and other resources. The lack of schools and other educational infrastructure and poverty raise particular challenges to the introduction of technology mediated UCL in the low (and medium) income countries. However, the barriers worldwide are similar and include lack of funding and other resources, lack of available technologies and specialists and lack of teacher education

Keywords: Inclusive culture, cultural components, typology inclusive culture, features of formation.

Main part: The practice of inclusive education for children with disabilities health opportunities (HIA) is marked by the intensive development of a culture of interaction with this contingent and declares the value, professional and personal attitude of teachers. Culture as a philosophical category reflects a certain historical stage in the development of society, identifies and describes target guidelines in forms of organization life and activity of people, their relationships, as well as in the material and spiritual values they create. Inclusive education is much broader than formal education. This is in education mostly works with children with learning disabilities. What are the qualities of an inclusive school teacher and educator in an inclusive kindergarten must have? Professional skills of the teacher are the main factor in inclusive education is considered First of all, the teacher must have an inclusive mindset and education teachers must take responsibility for the quality of inclusive education The main criteria of the quality of the teacher's work is that the students are of different categories protect and respect the rights of all children. Another quality - establish cooperation. Because it's collaboration and mutual thinking for teachers It is important to share. The teacher should systematically evaluate his activity, regularly improvement of skills, discipline and discipline of children with special educational needs leadership and management for institutions to work effectively with intergroups applying skills, solving problems together, comprehensive school it is necessary to have such qualities as establishing cooperation. It is known that in inclusive education, children with special educational needs are all children and are grouped according to different abilities for a specific purpose. If special education is carried out according to mental and physical appearance, inclusive education is determined according to the abilities and opportunities of the child. Special inclusive education when education is taught through special and alternative education programs child-centered and personalized, instructional, inclusive learning is taught on the basis of the program. The unique

and important aspect of inclusive education is that children and teachers learn from each other and solve problems together This education should not be one-sided.

Summary: Increasing self-confidence, developing skills and abilities in a child with disabilities, from a young age family involvement is important in promoting learning. It is also important to work with parents in the process of inclusive education. Highlight For parents with special needs, their children are a part of society to explain that they have the right to be, to convey this belief to their minds need Special attention is paid to this issue in the educational system of our country. 2020 year Our President, who was admitted in October, had special educational needs measures to further improve the system of education for children an example of this is the decision on in one school located in cities and districts of Tashkent city inclusive education will be introduced. Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent children with special educational needs in one school located in the city elementary basic classes will be opened for.

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